

WDP: Mitigating Interference in CPU Sharing Through Wake-up Delay Driven Preemption for QoS-aware Co-location

Supplementary materials for rebuttal

Reviewer-A-Q1: Evaluation Under Hardware Constrained Settings

Figure 1: The tail latency of 5 LC tasks and Job Completion Time (JCT) of BE task *bodytrack* when co-running on 8 cores

We evaluate WDP under the more hardware-constrained setting using the task combination in Section 9.2.1 in our paper. Specifically, we co-run the 5 LC tasks with a BE task. The loads of LC tasks are set to 50% of their max load (mid load). Compared with the original experimental setting in Section 9.2.1, we reduce the number of used cores from 16 to 8, while other settings remain unchanged.

Figure 1 shows the result when co-locating the five LC tasks and the BE task *bodytrack* (evaluating with other BE tasks shows similar results). During the experiment, the overall CPU utilization is over 90%. As shown in the figure, all strategies except Unmanaged ensure the QoS for all LC tasks. However, both ARQ and CLITE have to suspend the BE task *bodytrack* (no core is allocated to it), as they need to allocate all CPU cores to LC tasks to ensure their QoS requirements. Instead, WDP and RT allow BE tasks to utilize the unused CPU resources of LC tasks with CPU sharing. Furthermore, WDP adjusts the preemption capability of LC tasks to avoid excessive preemption of the BE task, thus boosting the BE throughput by 29.5% over RT.

Reviewer-B-Q2: Larger Scale Evaluation

To further evaluate WDP’s scalability, we re-run the experiment of Figure 19 of our paper. While keeping task configurations consistent with those in our paper, we increase the number of nodes from 4 to 8. We conducted 100 experiments. In each experiment, we randomly run one of the 7 selected BE tasks with 7 replicas on each node. Meanwhile, each node is randomly assigned 40 LC tasks (from the 5 selected LC tasks) to co-run. We manage the 8 nodes using WDP, ARQ, and CLITE, respectively, and record the average JCT of the 7 BE replicas for each node.

In the above 100 experiments, we obtained a total of 800 JCT results for each method (WDP, ARQ, or CLITE). We sort the JCT results in ascending order and index them from 1 to 800. As shown in Figure 2, WDP achieves 19.1% and 30.3% higher throughput than ARQ and CLITE.

Figure 2: The JCT of BE tasks in the 8- node evaluation.

Reviewer-C-Q1: Overhead of Hooks

We measure the overhead of eBPF hooks by using the function `bpf_ktime_get_ns()` to measure the execution time of eBPF functions attached to each eBPF hook. We present the CDF of the overhead of each eBPF hook in the following figures.

Figure 3: The CDF of overhead of eBPF hook 1.

Figure 4: The CDF of overhead of eBPF hook 2.

Figure 5: The CDF of overhead of eBPF hook 3.

Figure 6: The CDF of overhead of eBPF hook 4.